

WATER ABSORPTION OF BITUMEN-CONTAINING WATERPROOF MATERIAL

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Abstract. *The article presents the results of water absorption of waterproof material of the bitumen mastic type. The main components for creating waterproof material are bitumen produced at Fergana Oil Refinery and pyrolysis distillate from Ustyurt Gas Chemical Complex, as well as selected fillers that are readily available in Uzbekistan. Thus, an effective product for the construction of structures based on the use of local and available raw materials was obtained. For the efficiency and durability of the waterproof material, an analysis was carried out on key characteristics.*

Keywords: *bituminous mastic, waterproof material, pyrolysis distillate, corrosion protection, erosion protection, water absorption.*

Introduction. It is known that the role of waterproof materials based on petroleum bitumen and their compositions in protecting building structures from the constant impact of aggressive humid environments and chemically aggressive liquids is invaluable in the world. In this regard, many methods that help protect against moisture in construction, such as grinding the surface of building structure parts, applying coatings, polishing and forming a protective layer, are important for increasing the service life of buildings and structures.

The development strategy of Uzbekistan defines the tasks of “Wide introduction of innovations into the economy, development of cooperative ties between industrial enterprises and scientific institutions”. In this regard, conducting scientific and practical research on the development of technology for obtaining composite waterproof materials from bitumen and pyrolysis distillate is of great importance [1].

It should be noted that waterproof paint is an effective multi-layer (usually 2-4 layers) waterproof coating created by painting and having a thickness in the range of 3-6 mm. This method is one of the most widespread and technologically advanced ways of providing waterproofing and anti-corrosion protection for concrete and reinforced concrete structures, as indicated in literary sources [2-4]. Waterproof paint is applied from the outside of enclosing structures. Preliminary, the working surfaces are leveled using a cement-sand mortar. The surfaces are thoroughly cleaned of dust, dirt, grease stains, and concrete sagging is removed, protruding reinforcement is cut off, and drying is carried out. Subsequent application of bitumen mastic (hot or cold) is carried out with a brush, roller or using a spray unit. It is important to note that hot compounds are applied in two layers, while cold mastic is sprayed, as emphasized in the source [5-7].

All these procedures are critical to ensure reliable adhesion of the bitumen waterproofing layer to the structure, since the effectiveness of waterproofing is achieved due to deep penetration of the material into the porous surface, as specified in the literature [8, 9].

Composite waterproofing, performed with high quality, must meet a number of key characteristics important for its effectiveness and durability:

- Demonstration of high adhesion strength to the substrate, ensuring reliable adhesion to the base.

- Formation of a monolithic and continuous film, eliminating the presence of swelling, bubbles and surface irregularities.

- Ensuring complete water resistance over the entire area of the bridge deck, as well as in the areas of connection with drainage elements and at expansion joints.

- Guaranteeing tightness at junctions with sidewalks, fences and other protruding structures.

- Maintaining stable strength and elasticity under the influence of long-term exposure to atmospheric conditions.

- Ability to maintain its waterproofing properties and integrity under the influence of operational loads during the functioning of the bridge structure.

- Ability to effectively bridge cracks, preventing their propagation.

- Resistance to the penetration of chloride ions, which is important for preventing reinforcement corrosion.

- Maintaining the adhesion strength under shear, ensuring the stability of the coating.

Minor impact of thermal load on the functional and physical characteristics of the material, guaranteeing its resistance to temperature changes.

Research method. Specific devices and materials are used to analyze the water-absorbing properties of the mastic: laboratory scales that comply with GOST 24104–88, a glass plate measuring 50×50×5 mm, a glass mercury thermometer in accordance with GOST 25544–87, a water container, a brush or spatula for applying the mastic, and filter paper. The mastic is carefully applied in one layer to a pre-weighed glass plate using a brush or spatula and left to dry for one day. Tap water should be boiled for 30 minutes and cooled to a temperature of (23 ± 2) °C before use [10, 11]. The testing process begins with accurately weighing the prepared sample, immersing it in water for 1 minute, then carefully blotting it with filter paper for 30–60 seconds and reweighing. The sample is then placed in water so that a water column of at least 50 mm is formed above it, and left for 24 hours. After the time has elapsed, the sample is removed, blotted with filter paper, and weighed again. The time interval from removing the sample to weighing it should not exceed 60 seconds.

The processing of the results consists of determining the amount of water absorbed by the mastic on a glass plate after 24 hours of immersion in water at a temperature of (23 ± 2) °C. The water absorption (w) of the waterproof material is calculated with an accuracy of 0.1 percent using a special formula.

$$w = \frac{m_3 - m_2}{m_1} \cdot 100\%$$

here, m_3 – mass of sample after testing in water for 24 hours, g;

m_2 – mass of the sample after testing in water for one minute, g;

m_1 - dry sample mass, g.

Results and discussion of the study. In the process of developing the waterproof material, we identified the following key stages of composition:

In the initial phase of bitumen mastic creation, the loaded bitumen is heated to a temperature range of 175-180 °C to achieve its complete melting. This ensures the preparation of the bitumen for further mixing with other components.

Mineral fillers are added to the molten bitumen, and the mixture is thoroughly mixed for 30 minutes to form a homogeneous mass. Intensive mixing throughout the entire manufacturing process is critical to ensure the homogeneity of the mastic. In this regard, specialized boilers equipped with mechanical mixing devices are used.

When the temperature drops to a range of 45-55 °C, pyrolysis distillate is gradually added to the mass. Slow mixing continues for 30 minutes until the mixture is completely homogeneous. It should be noted that at high temperatures, pyrolysis distillate can evaporate, which will lead to a decrease in the volume of the finished mastic.

In the course of developing the waterproof material, five different compositions were defined, each of which combines bitumen, pyrolysis distillate and various fillers. These compositions are characterized as follows:

The first composition includes 30% BN 90/10 bitumen and 70% pyrolysis distillate without the use of fillers.

The second composition contains 30% BN 90/10 bitumen, 65% pyrolysis distillate and 5% microcalcite.

The third composition consists of 30% BN 90/10 bitumen, 65% pyrolysis distillate and 5% kaolin.

The fourth composition combines 30% BN 90/10 bitumen, 65% pyrolysis distillate and 5% graphite.

The fifth composition includes 30% BN 90/10 bitumen, 65% pyrolysis distillate and 5% JSC "AGMK" industrial waste.

The main components for creating the waterproof material are bitumen produced at Fergana Oil Refinery and pyrolysis distillate from Ustyurt Gas Chemical Complex, as well as selected fillers that are readily available in Uzbekistan. Thus, an effective product for the construction of structures was obtained based on the use of local and available raw materials. The results of the study on water absorption of these materials are presented in Table 1.

Table 1

Results of tests of samples of composite waterproof material "KGM" for water absorption

Name of indicators	Experiments		
	1 layer	2 layers	3 layers
1-composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -70%, Without fillers			
Water absorption (w), % mass:	0,43	0,42	0,42
m_1 , gram	23,1	23,3	23,7
m_2 , gram	23,1	23,3	23,7
m_3 , gram	23,2	23,4	23,8
2- composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Microcalcite - 5%			
Water absorption (w), % mass:	0,42	0,42	0,41
m_1 , gram	23,5	23,8	24,2
m_2 , gram	23,5	23,8	24,2

m_3 , gram	23,6	23,9	24,3
3- composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Kaolin - 5%			
Water absorption (w), % mass:	0,44	0,43	0,42
m_1 , gram	22,7	23,0	23,3
m_2 , gram	22,7	23,0	23,3
m_3 , gram	22,8	23,1	23,4
4- composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Graphite -5%			
Water absorption (w), % mass:	0,45	0,45	0,44
m_1 , gram	22,0	22,2	22,6
m_2 , gram	22,0	22,2	22,6
m_3 , gram	22,1	22,3	22,7
5- composition Bitumen BN 90/10 -30%, Pyrolysis distillate -65%, Man-made waste of JSC "AGMK" -5%			
Water absorption (w), % mass:	0,39	0,39	0,38
m_1 , gram	25,3	25,5	25,7
m_2 , gram	25,3	25,5	25,7
m_3 , gram	25,4	25,6	25,8

The following procedure is used to analyze the water absorption of the KGM waterproof material. Initially, the prepared samples are weighed to an accuracy of 0.01 g. Next, they are immersed in water for one minute, after which they are carefully blotted with filter paper for 30-60 seconds and weighed again. Then the samples are placed in water so that the height of the water column above them is at least 50 mm, and are kept in this state for 24 hours. After this time, the samples are removed from the water, blotted again with filter paper and weighed. It is important that the time from the moment the sample is removed from the water until it is weighed does not exceed 60 seconds.

Fig. 1. Water absorption graph (w) of samples of composite waterproof materials of the KGM type with a thickness of 1 mm, 2 mm, 3 mm

Conclusion. As part of the testing of a waterproof material, its condition is observed on its surface for a specified period of time and at a given pressure level. If no traces of water are found on the surface of the sample during this time, i.e. no visible changes occur, the material is considered to have passed the test. This means that it effectively resists water penetration under these conditions.

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